

Dropouts and Suicides of Marginalized in Higher Education in India

Prof. Amita Charan

Janki Devi Memorial College, University of Delhi

Abstract: Dropouts and Suicides are considered one of the serious issues in developing countries. Still, in most South Asian countries, despite the higher dropouts and Suicides among youth, mental ill-health is not taken as a serious matter in educational planning and policy formulation. Suicides and Dropouts are reported in all premier institutions, central and state universities. The world's largest education system is facing several crises and challenges. Recently, the University Grant Commission (UGC) introduced the Promotion of Equity in Higher Education Institutions Regulations, 2026, replacing the old 2012 framework. Institutions are blamed for the improper implementation of the Reservation Policy of the Government of India, including IIMs, IITs and minority institutions (funded by the government). Inclusive education is one of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and various organisations are trying to achieve it. National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 claims to institutionalise the procedure to deal with discrimination in higher education. The goal of the regulation is "to eradicate discrimination only based on religion, race, gender, place of birth, caste, or disability, particularly against the members of scheduled castes and scheduled tribes, socially and educationally backward classes, economically weaker sections, persons with disabilities, or any of them, and to promote full equity and inclusion amongst the stakeholders in higher education institutions." Establishing social harmony is the prime responsibility of teachers in schools, colleges and universities. This article is about the existing discriminatory practices and formulating the necessary measures against discriminatory practices in higher education.

Key Words: Dropout, GER, SDGs, NEP, UCG, Suicides

Introduction: Higher Education in India lacks inclusivity in different forums, and the two genders are included very late in the patriarchal setup of higher education. Many other socially disadvantaged groups were not even allowed to enter higher education. In the social domain, the reservation was ensured for different groups such as minorities of India, deprived groups like SC ST and OBC, and geographical groups based on backwardness in geographical territories. Perhaps over the years quota for wards, non-resident Indians, persons with benchmark disabilities, sports, NCC, defence, freedom fighters, economically weaker sections, acid attack victims, transgenders, girls and other groups were ensured in higher education in various courses. In professional courses and law, specified seats were earmarked for girls in central universities and other institutions. There is no hue and cry for any other groups in education and in employment. The hostility is only for SC, ST and OBC due to deep-rooted caste-induced hate in the minds. There was no sufficient evidence of the existence of any caste-based society in India till the third century in any of the manuscripts, civilization or in housing and settlements. Even at Buddhist universities, many scholars from other countries and from religions received their education in Taxila, Magadhashila, Nalanda, Nagarjunakonda, Vikramshila, etc. But things have changed, and caste dynamics emerged in different parts of India. Caste dynamics became more complex globally with the conversion and migration of

people. Even the United States, the United Kingdom and several other countries are formulating policies for caste-based discrimination with an increasing number of cases.

A few powerful, privileged people used it as a powerful weapon against all other groups. The intention was to hold wealth, power and education. Moreover, there are cases where other disadvantaged groups are also held responsible for discrimination against SC and ST students in educational institutes. In Modern India, Dalits and women both were not allowed to enter educational institutions. In a conversation with the British government, Jyotiba Phule proposed a scholarship for women so that young women can study abroad. Mountstuart Elphinstone, Macaulay and Wilson Hunter reviewed the education system of then India. Calcutta Madrasa, Bengal Sanskrit College and a handful of other colleges were not permitting the downtrodden and women in these colleges till 1821. Only Brahman Teachers were allowed to teach in Maharashtra. The Peshwa were paying them 500000 Rupees as remuneration to teach Sanskrit. In 1821, the first all-women boarding college was started in Tirunelveli, and only a few elite women were allowed to take admission. Elphinstone proposed education for all; his idea was opposed by Peshwas and Brahmans (Minutes on Education). Finally, Elphinstone had to leave India due to the massive protests. English became the medium of instruction in India in 1835. Wood's Education Dispatch 1854 is considered the Magna Carta of Indian Education. In 1848, Phule couple started the first girls' school in Maharashtra for all the castes and religions. The journey of inclusive education in India started from this school. Later, the couple started maternity homes, day care centres, orphanage homes, and widow shelters for all the castes etc. In 1882, the Hunter Commission was appointed to review the status of education. Lord Curzon initiated important decisions to improve higher education in India, and the Report on Indian Universities was submitted in 1902. The Indian University Commission was incorporated in 1904. There were only three universities in India in Calcutta, Madras and Bombay. In 1928, the Simon Commission was appointed to review the status of education in India. The commission disclosed the disparities and caste-based discrimination in education. A nationwide protest, "Simon Go Back", was organized by Lala Lajpat Rai, Gandhi ji, the Muslim League, and the Indian National Congress. Dr. Ambedkar was in favour of implementing the recommendations of the Simon Commission. The struggle of the marginalized is not yet ended. Whenever any bill or law is framed or amended to protect the marginalized and women, it is always opposed in our country.

Presently Maximum caste-based atrocities are faced by Scheduled caste and Scheduled tribe students as per the records of the National Crime Bureau, National Commissions and University Grant Commission. In the modern context, many vice-chancellors, principals, panellists, PhD guides, and faculty members are accused across different universities of exhibiting caste-based attitudes. Rohit Vemula, Payal Tadvi, Darshan Solanki, Manish Kumar and several other students lost their lives due to caste-based discrimination.

Despite all that, the institutions are not ready to fill the earmarked faculty positions of marginalised groups, and till 2024, 80% seats of OBCs and 83% seats of ST professors were vacant in Universities. Moreover, the representation of SC, ST and OBC faculty members at the top level is almost negligible in Central Universities, IIMs and IITs. 21 IIMs have fewer than 200 SC, ST, OBC teachers. None of the IIMs directors is from marginalized community. IIM Lunknow, Bangalore, Ahmedabad are the worst performers, Jammu has one ST teacher on roll, and Calcutta has none. The only available public data shows there are 62 SC, 16 ST and

109 OBC teachers, against 1180 total seats. Maximum students leave their courses in Central Universities, IITs and NITs due to caste-based discrimination.

Recently, UGC noticed a sharp increase in caste-based discrimination cases in higher education over the last five years. Many psychological problems occur due to caste-based discrimination, and the youth are trapped in the loops of hate in educational institutions. Many officials and Higher authorities are found guilty, and they are setting a wrong precedent among scholars and students across the globe. Neither do they understand the essence of education, nor do they understand the importance of the reservation system. There is no sensitisation program about caste, gender, race and disability-based atrocities in educational institutions, and there is no students' forum to continuously aware children about the representation of various social groups on different forums is essential. Many institutions do not allow for a simple discussion on Ravidas, Ambedkar, Periyar and Phule ideologies of inclusion in 21st century. Many universities even ignored the notification of UGC about the setting up of an Ambedkar Chair for Research and Development. Sign language and gender sensitisation training are not provided during orientation or refresher to the faculty members to deal with students with diversified background. Supportive infrastructure is not developed for differently-abled students. One side, Laws and rules related to discriminatory practices are not explained to the teachers, administrators and instructors. On the other side, a large number of parents brainwash their own children about caste, gender, disability, etc., and later many children suffer from **Personality disorders, Narcissistic disorder, superiority complex** or some **other type of mental illness**. In such a scenario, he or she cannot treat another person equally, capable of doing something or maintaining human dignity in the public domain. Moreover, to whom they treated as unequal or low also face several psychological issues, isolation, and develop suicidal tendencies in the long-run. Hence, the whole agenda of establishing equality through representation is not fulfilled.

Crime and atrocities are outcomes of psychological imbalance in the personality of social criminals who want to declare others as low and inferior. It is essential to identify the actual social criminals who are contaminating the educational environment. The sensitive, receptive and progressive people from all the communities are ready to develop an inclusive environment for teaching-learning for every group and each student. Provoking someone to commit suicide is an offence in the Bhartiya Nyaya Sanhita; not every child can face trolling or caste, gender or race-based abuses in public. Many children are out of education due to misbehaviour, caste-based abuses, trolling, public embarrassment, racial comments and atrocities. Caste is a hierarchical system inducing inequality among social groups without any justified grounds. For the protection of all the social groups, their representation must be ensured at a higher level and in all higher academic bodies and decision-making bodies. Over the years, caste has been considered a closed group where marriages in same group are allowed. Many honour killing cases and mob lynching cases are reported in India in different states. Now, caste-based discrimination is spreading in different countries and among different religious groups due to globalisation, migration, conversion, and tourism. According to UGC the caste-based discrimination in universities and colleges have risen by 118.4% over the past five years. The details submitted by Equal Opportunity Cells (EOCs) and SC/ST Cells to the parliamentary standing committee (704 universities and 1553 colleges) are mentioned below:

Cases Submitted to Equal Opportunity Cells/SC and ST Cells	
Year	Number of cases
2019-20	173
2020-21	182
2021-22	186
2022-23	241
2023-24	378

In some universities and colleges, Equal Opportunity cells are almost inactive and not registering any complaints, or the convenors are not representing any case related to marginalized community, transgender students, female students or students from north-east states. Moreover, for developing a healthy educational and learning environment, teachers must play a key role in curbing caste-based, gender-based and race-based discrimination. The teachers must be trained to teach without any caste or gender bias in their minds. Globally, cases of caste-based abuses are reported, and some countries even framed guidelines and procedures to handle caste-based discrimination in educational institutions.

Increase in the Number of Student Suicides in IITs, IIMs, NITs, AIIMs and CUs		
Year	Number	Students' Suicides (only) in IITs
2018	20	8
2019	20	8
2020	13	3
2021	10	4
2022	25	9
2023	15	3 (Till 3 rd April 2023)

*2023 data is collected till 3rd April, 2023

Between 2021-22 the reported cases of suicides in these institutions were more than double, and 33% cases are reported from IITs.

In India, many suicides are reported in premier institutions and central universities. IITs, NITs and Central Universities are reporting maximum cases of suicides. In case of dropouts, a staggering 25,593 students from reserved categories, including Schedule Castes (SC), Schedule Tribes (ST), Other Backward Classes (OBC), and other minority groups, have dropped out of central universities and IITs over the past five years.

If we observe the data maximum suicides are reported from IITs, Central Universities and NITs. Global Ranking, Internal Quality Assurance, NAAC Accreditation, Audits, Placement and Success Rate are meaningless if premier institutions in India can not control caste-based discrimination. They are not even able to develop a conducive and healthy educational environment for teachers and students. Moreover, for a single suicide entire institute is responsible.

IIT and medical aspirants work hard to clear the entrance exams, and after joining the course, if any student is thinking about dropping out, it is solely the responsibility of that institute. Differently abled people are still finding that the campuses are not inclusive for them. But the form of caste discrimination is entirely different, and it is developing hate among various groups, where SC, ST and OBC together constitute more than 85% population of the country. Economically weaker sections and women are not considered untouchables. Whereas the largest section of society is called as untouchable in public by a few mentally sick people, even they consider all other castes as low when it comes to the marital relations of their children. For this reason, many meritorious marginalised individuals are not getting a chance to enter higher education, to take a good job, to commence business, and to get a life partner of their own choice. Most higher positions in the private sector are filled through nepotism and referrals. Overall, caste atrocities are increasing in India, but surprisingly, in higher education, most educated and highly qualified people are engaged in caste-based discrimination. It means the institutions have failed to implement the inclusive policy of the government in higher education and to educate the students about the true essence of representation. It is solely the responsibility of the government to protect the lives of students in higher education institutions and to ensure the safety of staff and students administrative officers are appointed. In case they are not performing their duties, it is an administrative failure. Further, the internal complaint committees, equal opportunity cells and convenors are responsible for not handling the caste-based discrimination cases in the institutions in the early stages.

Cases registered under crime against Scheduled Castes/ Scheduled Tribes during the year 2013-2022

Year	Number of Cases registered		
	SC	ST	Total
2013	39408	6793	46201
2014	40401	6827	47228
2015	38670	6276	44946
2016	40801	6568	47369
2017	43203	7125	50328
2018	42793	6528	49321
2019	45961	7570	53531
2020	50291	8272	58563
2021	50900	8802	59702
2022	57582	10064	67646

Source:- National Crime Records Bureau, Ministry of Home Affairs

The details of caste-based cases of discrimination are mentioned in the table. Although a few cases caused global defamation, such as Seema Sigh, a senior faculty member from IIT Kharagpur, who was abusing marginalised students publicly. IIM Bangalore case, Periyar University case, IIT Mumbai case, Hyderabad University Case, Kakatiya Medical College case were also highlighted in the media.

In 2007 Thorat committee was set up to deal with caste-based discrimination in higher education. The committee was headed by Professor SK Thorat (chairperson), and accompanied by Dr K.M. Shyampradasa and Dr. R.K. Srivastava as members. In 2012, Equal Opportunity Cells and SC/ST cells were set up in the educational institutes. But most of the convenors in these cells were not from marginalised groups of backward communities. In 2019, UGC asked every university to set up the Ambedkar Chair and the SC, ST cell. In 2020 and 2022, UGC had asked all the higher educational institutions to ensure that no official and faculty members indulge in any form of caste discrimination against Schedule Caste (SC) and Schedule Tribe (ST) students. The National Commission also supported the efforts of UGC. Recently, UGC introduced the Promotion of Equity in Higher Education Institutions Regulations, 2026, replacing the old 2012 framework.

On the other side, the reservation system of India is appraised on different forums, and recently it was well appreciated by the World Economic Forum. For other social groups, there are traditional stigmas in society, like most transgender and differently abled children are disowned by their own parents and kept deprived of education. The attitude of society is hateful, and they are not ready to include them in the mainstream. The same stigma persists in employment and the workplace in our country. In medical and engineering college the social support system is very poor for needy students.

In eight IITs and seven IIMs, 80% faculty is appointed from the general category, and the reservation policy is completely neglected in the appointments. Medical colleges, engineering colleges and central universities are known for quality education, a healthy environment and advanced teaching, learning and research. Moreover, assessment, accreditation, and internal quality checks are their routine tasks. Most educated, intelligent and talented people are groomed in these institutions over the past four decades. Unfortunately, these institutions are not capable of developing a healthy atmosphere for teaching-learning.

The rate of suicide in Asia is highest after Sub Saharan region. Surprisingly, students are committing suicide in medical school, where they are trained to save the lives of others even under stressful circumstances and disasters. Mental health includes suicide attempts, Self-harm, depression, addiction, disorders, aggressive behaviour, etc. The National Medical Commission constitutes a task force to handle the dropouts and suicides in medical colleges. According to an RTI response by the National Medical Commission, in the last 5 years, 122 suicides and 1270 dropouts have been reported in medical colleges. Out of 122 medical students, 58 were studying in PG courses. Out of 1270 dropouts, 1117 were enrolled in PG.

It was estimated by the National Medical Commission of India that 25-26 students commit suicide in medical colleges. Over 13500 SC, ST and OBC students dropped out of Central Universities, IITs and IIMs as per the data tabled in Lok Sabha in 2023.

The details of students who committed suicide in medical colleges in all the states are presented in the table.

State/UT-wise details of medical students committed suicide during last three years

S. No.	Name of the State/UT	2020	2021	2022
1	Andaman & Nicobar Islands	0	0	0
2	Andhra Pradesh	2	0	1
3	Arunachal Pradesh	0	0	0
4	Assam	0	0	0
5	Bihar	1	0	0
6	Chandigarh	0	0	0
7	Chhattisgarh	0	0	0
8	Dadra & Nagar Haveli	0	0	0
9	Delhi	1	0	0
10	Goa	0	0	0
11	Gujarat	4	4	2
12	Haryana	2	0	0
13	Himachal Pradesh	0	0	1
14	Jammu & Kashmir	0	0	1
15	Jharkhand	0	1	0
16	Karnataka	4	1	1
17	Kerala	2	2	1
18	Madhya Pradesh	1	0	0
19	Maharashtra	3	3	5
20	Manipur	0	0	0
21	Meghalaya	0	0	0
22	Mizoram	0	0	0
23	Orissa	0	1	2
24	Puducherry	1	0	0
25	Punjab	0	0	0
26	Rajasthan	3	1	3
27	Sikkim	0	0	0
28	Tamil Nadu	0	2	2
29	Telangana	0	1	0
30	Tripura	0	0	0
31	Uttar Pradesh	2	1	2
32	Uttarakhand	1	0	0
33	West Bengal	2	0	1

Source:- National Medical Commission.

Details of UG Medical students committed suicide and last five years drop out

S. No.	State	Number of suicides		Number of Drop outs	
		Number of the Colleges	Number of Students	Number of the Colleges	Number of Students
1	Andhra Pradesh	3	5	6	13
2	Bihar	1	1	5	18
3	Chhattisgarh	0	0	1	3
4	Delhi	1	1	1	3
5	Gujarat	4	5	5	17
6	Haryana	1	1	1	1
7	Jammu & Kashmir	1	1	1	1
8	Jharkhand	1	1	0	0
9	Karnataka	4	5	8	17
10	Kerala	9	9	4	8
11	Madhya Pradesh	0	0	1	1
12	Maharashtra	3	3	5	12
13	Mizoram	1	4	1	2
14	Orissa	2	3	3	5
15	Pondicherry	2	3	2	3
16	Punjab	0	0	1	3
17	Rajasthan	3	5	3	4
18	Sikkim	1	1	0	0
19	Tamil Nadu	4	8	5	8
20	Telangana	1	1	3	3
21	Uttar Pradesh	4	4	5	15
22	West Bengal	0	0	5	15

The details of

Details of PG Medical students committed suicide and last five years drop out

S. No.	State	Number of suicides		Number of Drop outs	
		Number of the College	Number of Students	Number of the College	Number of Students
1	Andhra Pradesh	1	1	9	38
2	Assam	0	0	2	30
3	Bihar	1	1	2	5
4	Chandigarh	0	0	1	25
5	Chattisgarh	1	1	1	4
6	Delhi	2	2	7	155
7	Goa	0	0	1	2
8	Gujarat	6	9	11	103
9	Haryana	1	1	3	27
10	Himachal Pradesh	1	1	1	1
11	Jammu & Kashmir	0	0	1	30
12	Jharkhand	0	0	1	3
13	Karnataka	4	11	23	96
14	Kerala	1	1	6	10
15	Madhya Pradesh	1	1	4	17
16	Maharashtra	8	11	21	85
17	Manipur	0	0	2	10
18	Meghalaya	0	0	1	1
19	Orissa	1	1	3	13
20	Pondicherry	2	4	3	6
21	Punjab	0	0	4	15
22	Rajasthan	4	6	7	98
23	Sikkim	0	0	1	1
24	Tamil Nadu	1	1	17	39
25	Telangana	0	0	4	41
26	Uttar Pradesh	4	5	14	117
27	Uttarakhand	1	1	5	103
28	West Bengal	0	0	6	20

Conclusion: The approach in handling root causes of dropouts and suicides should be centred on criminals and powerful decision makers. Students come from diverse backgrounds, and teachers must be sensitive about caste-based discrimination in higher education institutions. In most institutions, teachers and staff members are not trained to handle students from different socio-economic communities and social groups. On one side, caste-based economic discrimination and caste-based social discrimination are depriving a large segment of society from using the resources and living life with self-respect. On the other side, fair representation of all marginalised groups at the top level can change the future of many people, but to ensure it, the proper implementation of the Reservation policy of the Government of India is necessary.

Race, colour, gender, and ethnicity are natural constructs, but caste is fabricated by a group of society to declare them superior and meritorious. To prove their meritocracy, a social network is framed to promote only privilege. In the earlier sections, it is discussed that only privilege were allowed to take admissions in Indian universities. Therefore, proper implementation and execution of policies related to marginalized groups are essential to adopt a top-down approach and to appoint vice chancellors from various categories. Henceforth, the representation of all the groups must be ensured from top to bottom, including private and public institutions. The Equity Cells and Ambedkar Chairs cannot function properly until the representation of various social groups is ensured through a sound policy framework and surveillance. The limitations of the reservation policy are reviewed, and it is recommended by many scholars that the reservation policy must be extended to the private organisations, entrepreneurial units, strategic business units, etc. In higher education, the representation of marginalized groups must be ensured in all academic and administrative bodies. The fellowship amounts, sponsorship, scholarship and other research funds must be equally distributed for establishing financial equity.

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